

THE DEVELOPMENT OF METHODS FOR CRANE-LESS LIFTING OF LONG-SPAN ROOFS

Ignatenko O.O.

Ph.D., doctoral student of the Department
of Construction Technologies of Kyiv
National University of Construction and Architecture, Ukraine
ORCID.org/ 0009-0009-7691-884X

***Abstracts.** The article discusses known examples of crane-free lifting of long-span roofs. An analysis of methods and technological solutions for moving roofs to the design height with the support of growing columns. The columns were grown up with the help of hydraulic jacks. A common disadvantage of the known solutions for lifting roofs by the column growing method is the hinge scheme of column-foundation interaction during column growing and vertical movement of long-span roofs. To ensure the verticality of the roof lifting process, large safety structures and extra hydraulic jacks were used. The need to continually monitor the synchronized operation of 8 to 16 hydraulic jacks was the reason for the slow and labor-intensive lifting of roof structures. The advantages of the method of lifting roofs with the support of growth columns include the concentration of all assembly processes for lifting the roof at the lower design marks. Hydraulic jacks were used to grow the columns at the level of the foundation marks. The disadvantages and advantages of the known solutions for crane-less lifting of long-span roofs were taken into account when developing a new crane-less lifting method.*

The special characteristic of the new technological solution is the usage of the project columns as guides when lifting the roof to the designed height. The roof is moved using mounting columns supported by hydraulic jacks that are installed on the

foundations. The mounting columns are grown between two project columns that are paired together. In order to facilitate the vertical lifting of the roof and the growth of the mounting columns, guidelines are used. The guides are attached to the project columns along their entire height. At the base of the project columns, securing clamps are attached. These clamps are used to grow up sections of the mounting columns. The long-span roof is lifted to the design height with the support of the growing mounting columns. After the long-span roof is fixed at the design height, the mounting columns are dismantled. The use of the developed method for growing the mounting columns using project columns will enable the roof to be raised to the desired height in 2 to 3 workdays. The new crane-free lifting method can also lift heavy technological equipment inside plant buildings when crane technology is not available.

Keywords: *forced displacement methods, crane-free lifting, long-span roof, hydraulic lifting device, growing columns, stepper hoist.*

Problem formulation. During the construction of industrial objects, the most difficult is the assembly of large-span roof structures weighing more than 1000 tons. When using traditional crane methods of free lifting of structures [1, p.91], it is necessary to use complex scaffolding and assembly platforms at a height of 14 - 34 m. At the same time, the time intervals for delivery of roofing elements to the project site are very long. Installation work on the formation of long-span roofs only with the help of cranes is very laborious and is defined as economically unprofitable. An attractive option from the point of view of organization, technology, duration and cost of work on the construction of long-span roofs is the option that combines crane and crane-less assembly methods. During the starting organizational and technological stage of mounting works, cranes are used to assemble foundations, projection columns and assemble roof blocks on low scaffolding [2, c.57–59]. At the next stage of building works, the structural and technological block of the roof is moved to the design height using crane-free technologies [3, c.12-14]. Common to

several options for the forced movement of long-span pavements to the design marks are the methods of column growing using hydraulic lifting units [4, c.50-52]. Improving the well-known technologies for crane-less lifting of roofs using hydraulic hoists is an urgent and relevant problem.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The development of scientific and theoretical solutions for constructing industrial facilities with long-span structural and technological blocks of roofs was carried out by well-known Ukrainian and foreign scientists. Among Ukrainian scientists, the greatest contribution to the development of technological solutions for the construction of roofs of industrial facilities using traditional crane and crane-less technologies was made by Shtol T.M., Fedorenko P.P., Shkromada A.A., Nazarenko V.F., Sytnik N.P., Balytskyi V.S., Topchii V.D., Tonkacheiev G.M., Chernenko V.K., Nizhnikovsky G.S. [1-6]. Among foreign scientists, a great contribution to the development of scientific and theoretical solutions for crane and crane-free technologies for the construction of roofs of industrial and civilian objects was made by L. Rówinski, K. Fidler, K. Fliger [7, 8].

Purpose and tasks of the article. In this work, the aim was to study the known organizational and technological solutions for the forced lifting of long-span pavements by the method of column splicing and, based on the analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of existing solutions, to develop new technologies for lifting structural and technological blocks of pavements. The roofing was lifted by relying on the mounting columns, which were grown up. At the same time, the growth of the mounting columns is carried out between the guides, the function of which is performed by the project support columns.

Presentation of basic material. This article presents a detailed analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of organizational, technological, and structural and technical solutions for crane-free lifting of long-span pavements that were moved to the design height with the use of extension columns. Given the location of hydraulic lifts under the growing columns, the method of columns' growing is classified as "lower columns' growing" [3, p.35]. A typical example of lifting a long-span roof by

the method of growing with the relying on project columns (Fig. 1, a) is the construction of a hangar in Abington, Great Britain in 1957 by Ove Arup and Partners and John Laing and Son Ltd. [8, c.20]. The roof consisted of three monolithic reinforced concrete segments (plan dimensions of each segment were 33.53 x 59.59 m) and was rested on four concrete columns (total weight of the roof was 1400 tons). The process of lifting the roof with the relying on the growing project columns is shown in Fig. 2. The concrete columns were made of T-segments. The weight of each T-segment was 500 kg, and the total number of assembled segments was 1000 pcs. Four hydraulic jacks were used to grow each column. The lifting capacity of each jack is 200 tons. In the process of growing, a space was formed between the inner side faces of the mounted T-segments. Reinforcing bars (14 bars for each column) were placed in the cavity as the column segments were grown. After the last T-segment of the column was installed, the cavity was filled with concrete and the reinforcing bars were tensioned after the concrete reached the design strength. The direct lifting of each monolithic roof segment took five days and involved 30 workers. Taking into account the time required for the concrete placed in the cavities of the segmental reinforced columns to reach its design strength and the tensioning of the reinforcing bars, the total time required to raise the pavements to the design height was 35 days.

The disadvantages of the present technology of lifting the roof block by the method of column growing include the hinged scheme of the column resting on the foundation during the growing process, significant labor intensity and low productivity of the assembly process, a large number of assembly operations to prepare for the growing of each T-type segment of the columns and the holding of individual blocks weighing 500 kg during their installation on the foundations in the growing zone, the need to constantly monitor the synchronous operation of 16 hydraulic jacks involved in lifting and holding the segments of the columns.

Fig. 1. Variants of lifting the roof by means of the growing method: a- with relying on the project columns, b – with relying on the mounting columns without vertical guides, c - with relying on the mounting columns using vertical guides, “A” – growing unit, 1 – roof, 2 – section of project column, 3 – growing project column, 4 – one-piece project column, 5 – section of mounting column, 6 – growing mounting column.

Fig. 2. The process of lifting the roof with the relying on the growing project columns: “A” – growing unit, 1 – hydraulic jack, 2 – T-type segment.

The lifting of a large-span roof by the method of growing with support on the mounting columns without the use of guides (Fig. 1, b) was performed when the roof of a hangar measuring 144 x 275 m [9] was erected with a span of 60 / 24 / 60 m at an aviation plant in Kyiv, Ukraine. The roof with an area of 39600 m² and a weight of 1100 tons was lifted to a height of 24 m in 12 shifts. In the process of lifting, the blocks of the long-span roofing were resting on the extension assembly columns,

which were the barrels of the PG-300 hydraulic lifts. The process of lifting the roof with the relying on the growing mounting columns is shown in Fig.3.

Fig. 3. The process of lifting the roof with the relying on the growing mounting columns: 1 – roof, 2 – one-piece project column, 3 – growing mounting column

The disadvantages of the present roof lifting technology include the difficulty of placing the roof blocks on the column heads and joining the raised roof blocks together at a height of 24m. At the same time, the final placement of the blocks at the design height was carried out by repeatedly repeating the "lift-lower" cycles within the height range of 200-300 mm with constant adjustment and control of the joints of large-sized roofing blocks. Taking into account that the lower growth of the PG-300 lift barrels defines the interaction scheme of the lift pillars with the foundations as "hinged", expensive and metal-consuming measures were implemented to ensure the verticality of the lift column sections during their growth. For this purpose, the sections of the hoist pillars were designed with dimensions of 4.0 x 4.0 m in plan, and the supporting vertical conductor of each hydraulic lift unit with a height of 10 m had

a lower frame contour with dimensions of 16 x 16 m [3, p.123-124]. It was also required to use sophisticated safety equipment with a special system of jacks that controlled the structural and technological unit during its lifting. In order to ensure the concentration of all processes for growing the lift barrels at the lower design marks, control the verticality of the lifted roof due to the guides used by the project columns, reduce the cost and reduce the time of installation work, a technology was developed to move the structure of a long-span roof to the design height with support during the lifting process on the mounting columns used as lift barrels [10].

The variant of lifting the roof by the method of growing with the use of lift trunks using guides is shown in (Fig. 1, c). The columns of the supporting frame of the structure are rigidly fixed in the foundations.

Performing the function of guides, the columns ensure the verticality of the lift shafts and transform the interaction scheme "foundation - lift column" from hinged to steady. Hydraulic jacks GD-170/1120 [2, p.124] are used as power units for raising the lift trunks and pushing the roof structure to the design height. The sequence of lifting the roof by the method of growing with the use of lift barrels using guides is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. The process of lifting the roof with relying on the mounting columns using vertical guides: a – roof structure in the process of lifting, b - phases of erection column raising, 1 – roof, 2 –project column, 3 - section of mounting column, 4 - growing mounting column, 5 - hydraulic jack

According to the developed technological solution, at the same time as the consolidation of structural and technological blocks of coating on low scaffolding works on the formation of a load-bearing transverse frame of the building from the foundations, load-bearing columns and intercolumn ties. Outside the design columns, hydraulic lifting units are installed on the foundations. On the columns, at the upper point of movement of the hydraulic jack rods, fix the lifting clamps and feed the heads of the lift barrels into the intercolumn space. According to the calculations, the lifting of a roof weighing 1200 tons to a height of 34 m can be provided in 3 workdays. When using the method of column growing with the roof structure to be lifted on the hoist barrels using vertical guides, the size of the construction site can be reduced to the size of the structural and technological roof blocks to be lifted.

Conclusions and perspectives for further development

1. Based on the analysis of known solutions for crane-free lifting of long-span roofs using the column growing method, a new method of crane-free lifting was developed. According to the new method, the structural and technological unit of the roof is assembled during the assembly of foundations, project columns and intercolumn connections. The roof structure is assembled on low scaffolding. Assembly of foundations, columns and assembling of roofing units is made using crane methods. Further lifting of the structural and technological roofing unit to the design height is achieved by supporting the mounting columns. The mounting columns are raised by hydraulic jacks located on the foundations. The mounting columns are grown between twin projection columns. The projection columns ensure the verticality of the roof lifting and the growing of the mounting columns. After fixing the roof at the design height, the mounting columns are dismantled.

2. The number of processes using assemblers during the lifting of the roof has been reduced to work on fixing the roof structure in the final step of fixing the roof to the design height. All the processes of growing up the mounting columns are automated.

3. Promising directions for the use of the new method of column growing have been identified, namely the lifting of large-sized and heavy technological equipment in the spaces of production halls, when the use of cranes is technically impossible, and the lifting of structural and technological roof blocks of 100% readiness to heights exceeding 34 m using reinforced structures of the supporting column frame.

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